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Satisfaction with the Educational System in OECD Countries

The OECD calculates the satisfaction with the educational system in its member countries. The data is available for the period between 2017 and 2022.

Satisfaction with the educational system in OECD countries in 2022. At the top of the ranking is Norway, with a satisfaction score of 87%, closely followed by Finland at 85%. These two Nordic countries are known for their advanced educational systems, characterized by a strong focus on inclusivity, teaching quality, and pedagogical innovation. Norway, in particular, has implemented reforms that emphasize personalized learning and student well-being, contributing to a high level of satisfaction. Ireland and Switzerland share the third place with a score of 84%, also demonstrating high satisfaction with their educational systems. Ireland has made significant investments in higher education and vocational training, while Switzerland is renowned for its dual education system, which combines school education with practical apprenticeships. Denmark, with 80%, and Slovenia, with 79%, follow closely. Both countries place great emphasis on equity and quality in education, striving to ensure that all students have access to high-quality educational resources. Slovenia, in particular, has made significant strides in modernizing its curriculum and digital inclusion. Other Nordic countries like Iceland (78%) and the Netherlands (77%) also maintain high scores, confirming the success of Nordic educational models in general, characterized by strong support for teachers, a particular focus on early childhood education, and inclusive policies. Austria, Belgium, and Luxembourg, all with a score of 75%, represent a group of countries with stable and well-funded educational systems, although with specific challenges related to the integration of migrant students and linguistic differences. The Czech Republic, with 74%, fits into this context as an example of how Central Europe is improving its educational standards. Costa Rica (72%) is the first non-European country on the list, highlighting an educational system that, despite limited resources compared to European countries, has gained recognition for its commitment to continuous teacher training and promoting accessible education. Sweden (72%), the United Kingdom (72%), and France (71%) show similar satisfaction levels, with the United Kingdom facing significant challenges related to education funding and pressure on public schools. France, despite having a well-structured educational system, still needs to address issues related to educational inequalities. Israel (69%) and South Korea (68%) represent the Middle East and East Asia respectively, with Israel making great technological advancements in schools and South Korea being known for its rigorous educational system and strong academic pressure. Australia, Canada, and Mexico, all with a score of 67%, reflect the diversity of educational systems in the Americas. Australia and Canada are known for their inclusive systems and

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high participation rates in higher education, while Mexico faces significant challenges related to the quality of education in rural areas. Spain (67%) and Estonia (66%) are examples of countries striving to improve the quality of education through reforms and innovations. Spain has invested in teacher training and inclusion, while Estonia is at the forefront of integrating digital technologies into education. New Zealand, Poland, and the United States, with scores between 66% and 64%, show varying levels of satisfaction, reflecting the different challenges and strengths of their educational systems. The United States, in particular, faces issues of equity and disparities in educational resources. Lower in the ranking are Colombia and Greece, both with 63%, and Germany with 62%. Germany, despite its reputation for a robust educational system, is facing difficulties related to teacher shortages and regional disparities. Italy, with a score of 60%, indicates moderate satisfaction, with significant challenges related to modernizing the educational system and reducing the gap between northern and southern regions of the country. Japan, with 57%, shows a lower level of satisfaction compared to other developed countries, likely due to high academic pressure and issues related to student mental health. The Slovak Republic (56%), Latvia (53%), and Chile (50%) are in the lower part of the ranking, reflecting the challenges these countries face in improving educational quality and addressing social and economic inequalities. Finally, the countries with the lowest scores are Hungary (47%), Lithuania (37%), and Turkey (21%). These data suggest significant dissatisfaction and the need for substantial reforms in their educational systems to address existing issues, such as lack of resources, inadequate teacher training, and structural inequalities.

Satisfaction with the Educational System in OECD Countries between 2017 and 2022. Between 2017 and 2022, data on satisfaction with the educational system reveal significant changes in various countries, with some nations experiencing notable improvements and others recording concerning declines. Analyzing these data, interesting trends emerge that reflect the impact of educational policies, reforms, and socioeconomic conditions on the educational systems of different countries. Among the countries with the most significant improvements are Greece, Israel, and South Korea. Greece registered the highest absolute increase, rising from a satisfaction level of 43% in 2017 to 63% in 2022, with an absolute increase of 20 points and a percentage change of 46.51%. This improvement could be attributed to the country's efforts to reform its educational system and address the challenges posed by the economic crisis of previous years. Israel and South Korea also saw notable increases, respectively 30.19% and 30.77%, likely due to investments in educational technology and reforms aimed at improving teaching quality and accessibility to education. Another positive example is Estonia, which saw a 26.92% increase in satisfaction, rising from 52% to 66%. Estonia is often cited as a model of educational innovation, particularly for integrating digital technologies in schools, which could explain the increase in user satisfaction. Finland, known for its excellent educational system, also recorded a significant increase in satisfaction, with a 10 percentage point increase from 75% to 85%, demonstrating that even high-performing systems can further improve. On the other hand, some countries have registered a decline in satisfaction with their educational systems. Turkey saw the most dramatic decline, with a 31 percentage point decrease, falling from 52% to 21%, a negative percentage change of 59.62%. This drastic decline could reflect systemic issues such as the quality of teaching, economic and political conditions, and regional disparities in access to education. Other countries with significant declines include Chile and Hungary, which recorded decreases of 18.03% and 17.54%, respectively. In Chile, the decline in satisfaction might be related to educational inequalities and student protests that have marked recent years, while in Hungary, controversial educational policies and the centralization of the educational system might have contributed to the decrease in satisfaction. In some countries, satisfaction with the educational system has remained largely unchanged. Austria and Poland, for example, have not recorded significant changes, maintaining their satisfaction levels at 75% and 66%, respectively. This

could indicate stability in their educational systems, although not necessarily an improvement. Another interesting aspect is represented by countries that, despite a high level of satisfaction, have registered a slight decline. Ireland, which had an extremely high satisfaction level of 89% in 2017, saw a decrease of 5 percentage points, standing at 84% in 2022. This slight decline, although still high compared to other countries, might suggest the need for further improvements to maintain perceived excellence.

Clustering with K-Means Algorithm Optimized with the Silhouette Coefficient. The clustering analysis performed using the K-Means algorithm optimized with the silhouette coefficient identified two distinct clusters based on satisfaction data for the educational system in OECD countries for the years 2017, 2019, and 2022.

- Cluster 0: Australia, Austria, Belgium, Canada, Costa Rica, Denmark, France, Finland, Germany, Ireland, Luxembourg, Netherlands, Norway, Portugal, Slovenia, Spain, Sweden, Switzerland, United Kingdom, United States. These countries generally show a medium-high level of satisfaction and tend to maintain stability or slightly improve over time. For example, Finland and Norway show very high levels of satisfaction in 2022, with Finland increasing from 75 in 2017 to 85 in 2022, and Norway increasing from 77 to 87 in the same period.
- Cluster 1: Chile, Estonia, Greece, Hungary, Israel, Italy, Japan, South Korea, Latvia, Lithuania, Slovakia, Turkey. These countries tend to show lower levels of satisfaction and, in some cases, a decline over time. For instance, Turkey experienced a significant drop in satisfaction, decreasing from 52 in 2017 to 21 in 2022. Lithuania also shows a decline, dropping from 43 to 37 in the same period.

The cluster analysis clearly highlights two distinct groups of countries, with Cluster 0 representing countries with a generally positive and stable perception of the educational system, and Cluster 1 comprising countries with greater challenges and a more negative perception.

Conclusions. The satisfaction value for the educational system in OECD countries grew by an average of 2% between 2017 and 2022. There are countries where the satisfaction value for the educational system increased, such as Greece with a value of 46.51%, South Korea with a value of 30.77%, and Israel with a value of 30.19%. Conversely, there are countries where the satisfaction value for the educational system decreased, such as Hungary with -17.54%, Chile with -18.03%, and Turkey with -59.62%.

Declarations

Data Availability Statement. The data presented in this study are available on request from the corresponding author.

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Clustering Of Countries Based On Educational System Satisfaction (2017 Vs 2022)

Legend: Satisfaction in 2022 (yellow dot), Satisfaction in 2017 (orange dot), Cluster 0 (yellow square), Cluster 1 (orange square)

Satisfaction with the Educational System in 2022

Absolute Change in Satisfaction with the Educational System (2017-2022)